

A Closed Holographic Identity for the de Sitter Horizon

Planck energy equals Quantum action divided by Planck time

$$E_{Planck} = \frac{\hbar}{t_{Planck}}$$

Planck length is distance light travels in Planck time.

$$t_{Planck} c = l_{Planck}$$

If space expands one Planck length in every spatial direction it has volume of sphere with one Planck length radius. It is called "Planck sphere"; Volume of Quantum in Bulk.

$$V_{Planck} = \frac{4}{3} \pi l_{Planck}^3$$

Planck sphere energy density equals Planck energy divided by Planck sphere volume

$$\rho_{Planck\ sphere} = \frac{E_{Planck}}{V_{Planck\ sphere}}$$

Dark energy density depends on cosmological constant Λ

$$\rho_{\Lambda} = \frac{\Lambda c^4}{8 \pi G}$$

Number of Holographic Quanta equals Planck sphere energy density divided by Dark energy density.

$$N = \frac{\rho_{Planck\ sphere}}{\rho_{\Lambda}}$$

de Sitter-Space radius

$$r_{deSitter} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{\Lambda}}$$

de Sitter-Space horizon area

$$A_{dS} = 4 \pi R_{dS}^2 = \frac{12 \pi}{\Lambda}$$

de Sitter-Entropy

$$S_{dS} = \frac{\pi}{2} N k_B$$

de Sitter-Space horizon patch area equals de Sitter horizon area divided by Number of holographic Quanta. This the Quantum of Boundry.

$$A_{Boundary Quantum} = \frac{A_{dS}}{N} = 2\pi l_{Planck}^2$$

Total volume of Bulk Quanta equals Planck energy divided by Dark Energy density

$$V_{Bulk Quanta} = \frac{E_{Planck}}{\rho_\Lambda}$$

$$V_{Bulk Quantum} = \frac{V_{Bulk Quanta}}{N} = \frac{4}{3}\pi l_{Planck}^3$$

Holographic principle

$$N_{Bulk Quanta} = N_{Boundary Quanta} = \frac{6}{\Lambda l_{Planck}^2}$$

Cosmological constant

$$\Lambda = \frac{6}{N l_{Planck}^2}$$

Saturation

$$\frac{N \hbar G \Lambda}{6 c^3} = 1$$

Celestial Holography

de Sitter Horizon S^2 can be described as Riemann sphere coordinates